

University of Natural Resources
and Life Sciences, Vienna

BACHELOR THESIS

Comparing microbiomes of birch catkin aerosols

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Desired academic degree:
Bachelor of Science

Bachelor programme: Food Science and Biotechnology
Supervisor: Dipl.-Ing. Dr. Theresa Scharl-Hirsch

Vienna, 2022-04-26

Abstract

Pollen of birch trees are a frequent cause of allergic diseases, and the microbiomes of pollen were observed to contribute to their allergenic potential. To obtain an overview of the aerosolised microbiomes and to evaluate sampling methods, we collected birch catkins and sampled aerosols produced by them. The catkins themselves were sampled for comparison. Samples varied across different trees, stages of maturity of the catkins, and size fractions of the aerosols. Their microbiomes were analysed by amplifying characteristic parts of the 16S region of bacteria and the ITS region of fungi, and next generation sequencing. The sequencing data was aligned into a phylogenetic tree, and cross-referenced with the unite and RDP databases for taxonomic assignment. In parallel, a comparison between sequence data of different aerosol flows was performed. The microbiome data was evaluated regarding diversity and indicator taxa, with a focus on shaping upcoming sampling strategies. Differences found between samples taken with different collection methods indicate that the microbiome of the aerosolised components differs from that of the catkins, and possibly even by the aerosol size fraction. Given that distinct mechanisms of interaction between the microbiome and birch allergenicity are being researched, different microbiomes can be relevant. As that the microbiome is not homogeneous, its variation should be considered in sampling for further research.

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Integration of this thesis in collaborative bioaerosol research

This bachelor thesis is embedded in exploratory work on birch pollen and their aerosolised particles led by Julia Burkart at University of Vienna. Laboratory work regarding microbiome analyses was performed at AIT Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT) and supervised there by Clara Pogner. The work described in this text was performed by the author unless explicitly noted otherwise.

The author thanks Dragana Bandian for maintaining a well organized lab environment, Clara Pogner for providing both background information and practical advice, as well as Theresa Scharl-Hirsch for supervising the thesis and providing guidance on statistics.

Note on typographic conventions

Following the conventions set in the `jss` document class (Zeileis, 2021) for the Journal of Statistical Software (JSS), names of software packages are typeset **in bold** and programming languages *sans-serif*. As several file formats are mentioned, they are displayed in (usually capitalized, following the format’s naming style) *ITALICS*. If any of these are abbreviations, they are available for lookup in appendix C.

1. Introduction

Pollen allergies are a widespread and growing medical issue, and birches (*Betula*) produce the most allergenic tree pollen in central Europe (D'Amato et al., 2007). The bacterial and fungal microbiome of the pollen has been studied under two aspects: The presence of microorganisms can influence the concentrations of allergens such as the Bet v 1 protein, which is expressed by birches as a reaction to pathogens to protect itself (Obersteiner et al., 2016). These host defense mechanisms are associated with guard cells in the plant's epidermis (Khodai-Kalaki et al., 2015).

Microorganisms can also contribute more directly to allergic reactions to pollen, e. g. by their lipopolysaccharides (LPSs) causing inflammatory reactions (Manirajan et al., 2019).

Previous microbiome studies collected birch pollen by sieving of collected catkins, or did not specify their collection methods. Given that different mechanisms of microorganism contribution to allergenicity are located in different parts of the plant, a wider view on the catkin's and its aerosol's microbiome might be warranted.

1.1. Goals of the analyses

This work was performed to gain some initial insight into the bacterial and fungal microbiomes of aerosolised components of birch catkin. Sampling was spread across different trees and stages of blooming to find which factors influence the microbiome, and performed with different methods to find how the microbiome changes with the size of aerosolised particles. For that purpose, various characteristics (like diversity) needed to be calculated, samples to be mapped to established taxa, and properties of the samples to be correlated with groups of organisms. This was planned in the hope that insights obtained from this will help later studies of birch pollen microbiomes in picking their focus, e. g. by simplify future sampling through reduction to a set of relevant sampling methods.

As a separate goal, a simple test for partial flows of collected aerosols was described. Its intended application was to be run on microbiome datasets collected from a single atmosphere with different collection methods, and to detect unexpected differences in aerosol flows with minimal additional effort. If, in an experiment designed such that one sampling method collects a fraction of another method, the partial flow comparison would detect differences, a more detailed evaluation of that sampling would be indicated. This check would consider the quantity of reads at different levels in a constructed phylogenetic tree, and would thus report discrepancies even though they would otherwise be masked by the presence of other organisms. For example, if sampler A claimed to collect any particle between $0.5\ \mu\text{m}$ and $10\ \mu\text{m}$ and sampler B between $0.5\ \mu\text{m}$ and $2\ \mu\text{m}$, but some group of organisms were to be present primarily in sampler B, that would hint at inconsistent sampling efficiencies.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sample and processing overview

Branches of birch trees were collected from twelve different trees around Vienna. The branches with mature catkins were placed in a ventilated chamber; some twice at different stages of maturity. The outgoing air flow was sampled with different devices; in parallel, sedimented particles inside the chamber and catkins from the same tree were collected (section 2.2).

Sampled material was concentrated, cells disrupted, and the DNA extracted (section 2.3).

On parallel tracks, DNA sequences of characteristic regions in fungi (ITS region, section 2.5) and bacteria (16S, section 2.6) were amplified using nested polymerase chain reaction (PCR). On bacterial DNA, a primer pair that excludes chloroplasts was used; still, mitochondrial DNA would only differ from bacterial DNA by length, and was excised from an electrophoresis gel between the nested PCR steps. Both mitochondria and chloroplasts would, left unremedied, have made up a majority of reads and masked the bacteria. In addition to the samples passing through the regular process, cuts of the mitochondrial electrophoresis bands as well as products of a different primer pair that would not exclude plastids were prepared. All DNA products were amplified again with index markers for Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) (section 2.7.1), purified and pooled (section 2.7.2) and submitted for sequencing (section 2.7.3).

The resulting data was cleaned up, clustered, aligned into a phylogenetic tree, matched to established taxa, and correlated to properties of the samples (section 2.8). The tree and taxonomy data were matched for visualization and validation purposes (section 2.9). The read counts were also used to build a model distinguishing samples from different collection methods (section 2.10).

2.2. Sample origin and preprocessing

The steps described in this subsection were performed by Julia Burkart and the team at University of Vienna; they are listed in this text for context and are not part of the graded work.

Samples from twelve birch trees were collected from March to May 2021 in Vienna, Austria. Of each tree, one or two catkins were stored in tubes containing 5mL of 0.01% Tween buffer (see table 5 on page 31, which describes all used stock solutions) and frozen. A branch with several catkins was placed in a chamber ventilated with filtered air of constant temperature and humidity. A \varnothing 60 mm Petri dish was placed in the chamber to collect sedimented particles.

In the initial two samples, circular aluminium sheets coated with glucose were used to capture the sediment. The sheets were prepared by rubbing them in 1mL of a 60%_{m/v} glucose solution, letting them soak for four minutes, and overnight drying in a drying chamber. After sampling, the sheets were stored in 10mL Tween buffer and frozen.

That process turned out to be impractical due to varying success rates of the coating as well as due to crystallizing sugar. Later samples were captured directly in the Petri dishes and frozen inside them without any added liquid.

Air from the chamber was actively sampled using two devices: A Gesamtstaubprobenahme (GSP) sampler (see table 6 on page 32, which describes all used machines) operated at $3.5 \frac{L}{min}$ collected the inhalable dust fraction of the aerosol stream onto $\varnothing 37$ mm PC (polycarbonate) membranes with $0.4 \mu m$ pores. The device's description defers to DIN EN 481:1993 for the definition of inhalable dust without explicitly describing the collected fraction's particle sizes. After sampling, the membranes were placed in $5 mL$ Tween buffer and frozen.

In parallel to the GSP sampler, a cascade impactor was operated at $9 \frac{L}{min}$, collecting onto $\varnothing 25$ mm PC filters with $0.2 \mu m$ pores in each of its stages A (particles $\geq 2.5 \mu m$), B ($\geq 1.0 \mu m$), C ($\geq 0.5 \mu m$) and D ($\geq 0.25 \mu m$). Likewise, the membranes were placed in $5 mL$ Tween buffer and frozen. The filters of stages B to D were immediately aggregated in a single storage tube, as no differentiated findings were expected from the very latest stages.

Samplings were repeated when visual inspection indicated a change in the blooming stage; from one to three samplings were run on each branch. Subsequent sampling repetitions were not always conducted with all available methods.

2.3. Reduction of liquid and DNA extraction

All frozen liquid samples were thawed, thoroughly vortexed and cleared of solid components (catkins, filters, aluminium sheets). The samples were centrifuged, frozen and freeze dried.

Sedimentation samples in Petri dishes were suspended in $2 mL$ Tween buffer and transferred to tubes. Subsequently, the buffer was removed in a vacuum concentrator.

The extraction of DNA was performed using the Qiagen MagAttract Power Soil DNA EP Kit (QIAGEN, 2018). The kit's handbook was generally followed; both the over-all procedure and several deviations from the handbook are documented in appendix E. On the first set of samples (designated birch 03 / 04 / 05) it was performed manually; a second set was processed in a semi-automated fashion.

2.4. Initial explorative steps

To verify the success of the DNA extraction steps, an initial PCR run was performed using the FungiQuant primers, the GoTaq polymerase and the 55 00:45 35 programme¹. The extracted DNA was used as template in a dilution of 1:10, with additional undiluted and 1:100 runs on selected samples to track down handling mistakes later, and to get visual reads even on low concentrations. The presence of PCR product was checked visually under UV light after running $5 \mu L$ of PCR product for 30 min at $100 V_{DC}$ in a $2\%_{m/v}$ agarose gel (cast from stock solution as per table 5).

¹Primer pairs are described in table 3, polymerases table 2 and programmes in table 1 on page 7.

Name	T_{melt}	T_{anneal}	t_{elong}	N		Step	Temp.	Time
55 00:45 35	95 °C	55 °C	45 s	35	$N \times \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \\ \\ \\ \\ \end{array} \right.$	Melt	T_{melt}	30 s
F54 01:00 25	98 °C	54 °C	60 s	25		Denature	94 °C	30 s
F54 01:00 30	98 °C	54 °C	60 s	30		Annealing	T_{anneal}	30 s
F55 01:00 25	98 °C	55 °C	60 s	25		Elongation	70 °C	t_{elong}
F55 01:00 35	98 °C	55 °C	60 s	35				

Table 1: Named PCR programmes. All used PCRs are specified to use the sequence of the right table, with parameters from the left table filled in.

Mix name	Polymerase	Buffer	dNTP	Primer forward	Primer reverse	Template	Water (PCR)	Nominal total V
GoTaq	— 7.5 μ L	GoTaq mix 2 \times —	—	0.75 μ L	0.75 μ L	1 μ L	5 μ L	15 μ L
Q5	0.4 μ L	Q5 8 μ L	0.8 μ L	2 μ L	2 μ L	2.6 μ L	23.3 μ L	40 μ L

Table 2: PCR assay compositions, named after the used polymerase. The source of polymerase mix (GoTaq) or its components (Q5) is detailed in table 5.

Name	Source	Kingdom	Main usage
Forward and reverse sequence			
Fungiquant	Liu <u>et al.</u> (2012)	Fungi	Initial checks for DNA
F: GGRAAACTCACCAGTCCAG			
R: GSWCTATCCCCAKCACGA			
799 / 1392	Chelius and Triplett (2001) / Klindworth <u>et al.</u> (2012)	Bacteria	Sequencing pre-amp, organelle exclusion
F: AACMGGATTAGATACCCCKG			
R: ACGGGCGGTGTGTRC			
799 / 1175 Nextera	as above / Bonder <u>et al.</u> (2012)	Bacteria	Sequencing nested
F: TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGAACMGGATTAGATACCCCKG			
R: GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGACGTCRTCCCCDCCTTCCT			
ITS1F / TW13	Gardes and Bruns (1993) / Taylor and Bruns (1999)	Fungi	Sequencing pre-amp
F: CTTGGTCATTTAGAGGAAGTAA			
R: GGTCCGTGTTCAAGACG			
5.8S-Fun / ITS4-Fun + ITS43-Fun Nextera	Taylor <u>et al.</u> (2016)	Fungi	Sequencing nested
F: TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGGGAACCTTTYRRC AAYGGATCWCT			
R: GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGAAAGCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGCTTAART (50%), GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGAAAGCCTSSSCTTATTGATATGCTTAART (50%)			
341 / 785 Nextera	Klindworth <u>et al.</u> (2012)	Bacteria	Alternative sequencing
F: TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGCCTACGGGNGGCWGCAG			
R: GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGGACTACHVGGGTATCTAATCC			

Table 3: Primer pairs used. Sections designed not to match the sample but serving later processing are printed in grey.

The bands showed visible PCR product in all the initial samples, and a large dynamic range matching expectations of larger quantities in full-catkin samples than in the actively collected fractions. Based on that observation, the later samples were processed using the same methods.

2.5. Fungi amplification

Aliquots of the extracted DNA were used as template for a PCR run with ITS1F / TW13 primers, polymerase Q5 and the PCR programme F54 01:00 25. The primers were selected based on established AIT protocols built on Wessely (2020) to increase diversity (compared to only using the more specific primers of the nested PCR step). The polymerase was selected for its accurate replication of sequences. The programme was selected per the requirements of primers and polymerase (especially with an increased melting temperature to activate the polymerase).

This and following PCR runs were done in 384 well plates, with a 40 μL nominal reaction volume spread across groups of four wells. The odd volumes associated with the Q5 assay in table 2 result from scaling up a 15 μL process, and were of little concern in practice: all components except the template were loaded from a master mix. As Q5 polymerase is temperature sensitive, all steps were conducted on ice: master mix was prepared, distributed on a 96 well plate, loaded with samples, and distributed to a 384 well plate.

The PCR product was pooled from the four wells containing the same sample, and used as template in another PCR step. Here, the primer pair chosen was 5.8S-Fun as forward and an mix of ITS4-Fun and ITS43-Fun as reverse primers. The primers were used with indexing tag extensions (Nextera, Illumina) called “Read 1” (forward) and “Read 2” (reverse) in preparation for the indexing stage. The same polymerase (Q5) and layout (4 wells per sample) as in the first PCR run were used. The primer parameters indicated the programme F55 01:00 25.

This nested setup was chosen again based on Wessely (2020). Furthermore, a single equivalent amplification run would have exceeded the polymerase’s specified cycle number ($2 \times 25 - \log_2 \frac{40 \mu\text{L}}{2.6 \mu\text{L}} > 35$). The primers ITS4-Fun and 5.8S-Fun are also described (and neatly illustrated) by Taylor *et al.* (2016) to cover a wide range of fungi while rejecting other eukaryotes. The hairpin optimization described there is not applicable, the current Nextera tags were used here instead of the original Illumina tags used there.

The product was pooled and stored for later indexing.

2.6. Bacteria filtering and amplification

Aliquots of the extracted DNA were used as template for a PCR run with the 799 / 1392 primer pair targeting the DNA encoding the 16S ribosomal RNA, using Q5 polymerase and the programme F54 01:00 30. The 799 forward primer was described by Chelius and Triplett (2001) to exclude chloroplast DNA altogether, and to produce larger DNA fragments for mitochondria than for actual bacteria. The 1392 reverse primer was selected based on Hanshew *et al.* (2013).

To remove mitochondrial DNA, the PCR product was electrophoretically separated in freshly prepared, autoclaved 1%_{m/v} agarose gel, producing bands of about 600 bp (bacteria) and 900 bp (mitochondria). Unlike previously described gel runs (in which the GoTaq assay's PCR product could be loaded directly from the wells), here 5 μL product were each mixed with 1 μL 6 \times loading dye (Promega) before loading.

The bacterial segments were excised from the gel using hand punches (X-TRACTA Generation II 7 mm \times 2 mm, Biozym) under UV illumination. Filter tips (1000 μL , Expell) were prepared with their tips cut to sit on 2 mL tubes and autoclaved. The excised gel fragments were placed on the pipette end of the tips, and centrifuged through the filters into the tubes, producing between 20 and 100 μL of DNA containing liquid.

Several additional excisions were performed on arbitrarily selected strong 900 bp (mitochondria) bands; these were processed along with the other samples.

In a second amplification stage, the 799 / 1175 Nextera pair was used (with Q5 polymerase and the programme F54 01:00 25). The primer pair was selected from Bonder *et al.* (2012) and matches the length requirements of the sequencing step.

The pooled product was stored for later indexing.

For comparison, the primer pair 341 / 785 Nextera described by Klindworth *et al.* (2012) was used on arbitrarily selected samples with high DNA content (with Q5 polymerase, and the F55 01:00 35 programme used in a single amplification run).

2.7. Preparation for sequencing

2.7.1. Indexing

PCR products of the bacteria and fungi regions were prepared for sequencing by an index PCR run. At this stage, all templates contained consistent adapter sequences labelled "Read 1" in the forward direction and "Read 2" in the reverse direction. Table 3 shows these in grey.

The Q5 assay previously described was modified in this step for better handling: The total volume was halved to 20 μL , and the PCR was performed in 96 well plates (one per kingdom). Unlike in other assays, primers were not added as part of the master mix. Instead, 24 different primers matching the Read 1 tag were applied per column (12 each for the bacteria and fungi plates), and 8 different primers matching the Read 2 tag were applied per row (shared for bacteria and fungi). The PCR was performed using the F55 01:00 20 programme.

Subsequently, the presence and rough quantity of PCR product for each sample was verified using gel electrophoresis. PCR product was almost universally present, and mostly in similar quantity (with some errors already observed at pipetting time). Therefore, and to avoid the risk of additional pipetting errors, equal quantities of PCR product were taken from each well: 12 μL per sample were pooled into separate tubes for the fungi and the bacteria plate. The pools were vortexed and split into two 500 μL volumes each (designated A and B), simultaneously providing suitable volumes for the following PCR product purification step and material for a possible repetition of the sequencing process.

2.7.2. PCR product purification

The four pools (Fungi A, Fungi B, Bacteria A, Bacteria B) were processed through a PCR product purification kit (QIAquick PCR Purification Kit, Qiagen) following its instructions (QIAGEN, 2020, pp. 22–21).

Summarizing the kit process, the sample was mixed with binding buffer, and fed through a spin column containing a silica membrane. The membrane was designed to adsorb PCR product between 100 bp and 10 kbp under the acidic and high salt conditions of the binding buffer. An ethanol buffer was then used to remove the binding buffer. Finally, an elution buffer providing basic and low salt conditions was used to wash out the PCR product into a more pure and concentrated solution.

Noteworthy deviations from the kit process were:

- The initial binding steps were performed in five steps of up to 700 μL each, for the full 3000 μL (500 μL for the sample and $5 \times 500 \mu\text{L}$ of binding buffer) would have overflowed the tubes.
- The volume of Buffer PE (abbreviation not expanded in the kit description) was reduced from 0.75 mL to 0.70 mL to avoid overflows.
- The elution buffer (Buffer EB) was let soak 5 min before centrifugation because experience in the lab indicated that this generally improves the output.
- No pH indicator was added, as that step was not yet part of the dated (2000-04) version of the instructions originally used. (Also, that may or may not have later interfered with sequencing).

2.7.3. Sequencing

Concentration measurements and sequencing were performed by Clara Pogner at AIT and the Vienna BioCenter Core Facilities (VBCF) team, respectively, and not part of the graded work.

The DNA concentration in the four purified pools was measured using a spectrophotometer in microvolume mode to verify it was suitable for sequencing.

A pool of 15 μL of Fungi A and Bacteria A was submitted to VBCF for a next generation sequencing (MiSeq PE250 Nano) run. Along with the sample, VBCF was provided with a sample list indicating the used adaptors.

2.8. Data preprocessing and evaluation

Sequence data was provided by VBCF as an archive of reads in Binary Sequence Alignment Map (*BAM*) format. Reads were already demultiplexed and stripped of the indexing tags and tag extensions. The individual files contained between 462 and 8024 pairs of reads, each containing 250 bases and accompanying quality scores.

The data processing steps were guided by the recommendations of the “Moving Pictures” (general pipeline assembly), “Atacama soil microbiome” (for paired-end sequences), “Training feature classifiers” (for taxonomy) and “Predicting sample metadata values with **q2-sample-classifier**” tutorials provided as part of **QIIME** (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019).

Data import To import the data, the original files were converted into *FASTQ* format using **samtools** (Li *et al.*, 2009), and imported into **QIIME** artifacts based on import manifests enumerating the samples and their adaptors for bacteria and fungi on separate tracks.

To easily confirm that the right sets of data were converted to *FASTQ*, the non-tag parts of primers (indicated in black in table 3) were checked against the first base pairs of the *FASTQ* files (by viewing them in a text editor).

Bacterial reads from samples that diverged from the regular processing, e.g. those produced with different primers or by excising the mitochondria bands (see section 2.6) were removed before final processing because they could not possibly produce usable results in the next steps: the sequence lengths for mitochondria exceeded the double read size of the sequencing and thus did not produce usable paired reads in the next step; those using the 341 / 785 Nextera primers would have needed different database processing for taxonomic matching. (The sequences were part of preliminary exploration in the data set, and even processed up to the taxonomic assignments, but later discarded as their presence violated requirements of the used programmes).

Pairing and clean-up The forward and reverse reads were merged using the DADA2 algorithm by Callahan *et al.* (2016) as provided through the **q2-dada2** package. This algorithm simultaneously aligns the two paired reads, deduplicates reads differing only by noise, and removes chimeric reads, all considering the quality indication given in the original data. Given that both the fungal and bacterial fragments had lengths of around 400 base pairs, and that 250 base pairs were read in each direction, about 100 base pairs of overlap were available for verification.

The statistics provided by the DADA2 module’s stats output indicated a high noise level on several reads – in 20 samples, less than 20% of the reads passed the input filtering and denoising stage. These samples were spread across kingdoms, methods and birches. The rejection of the samples is consistent with the original *FASTQ* files indicating low per-base quality and sequences not matching the relevant primers. The source of these errors is unclear; a planned second more thorough sequencing of the data might be helpful in clearing this up.

Tree building The cleaned up sequences were aligned and grouped into a tree structure using the Multiple Alignment using Fast Fourier Transform (MAFFT) and FastTree algorithms. MAFFT was implemented by Katoh and Standley (2013), and aligns the sequences relative to each other based on the assumption that they are homologous. FastTree was implemented by Price *et al.* (2010), and infers evolutionary relationships

from aligned sequences. It heuristically approximates the tree that has the maximal likelihood of producing the observed sequences under an evolution model. Both are provided and combined in the **q2-phylogeny** package.

This tree structure was used for three main purposes: It provided a structure for visualizations (such as Figure 2) along with a moderately meaningful sorting order (where similar sequences are shown in proximity, but proximity does not necessarily imply similarity). It was also used for the flow comparison of section 2.11. When combined with taxonomic matches (see section 2.9), it was used as an additional check of the database results.

Taxonomic matching Independent of MAFFT tree building, the sequences were looked up in the unite (Kõljalg *et al.*, 2020; Nilsson *et al.*, 2018) and RDP (Wang *et al.*, 2007) databases for the fungal ITS and bacterial 16S regions, respectively. The databases each provide species hypothesis data for their reads, mapping DNA sequences onto taxa to the extent they are identified, often to the species level.

The RDP database was reduced to relevant segments by running in-silico PCR with the 799 / 1175 bacterial primer pair; this is a recommended step for the subsequent classification. The same step was not performed on the unite ITS database because the database is already trimmed to a relatively short region that does not always contain the full primers. For that reason, the step is not recommended for that database by the “Training feature classifiers” tutorial shipped with **QIIME**.

For classification, a multinomial Naïve Bayes classifier was trained on the (trimmed, in the RDP case) databases provided in **QIIME**’s **feature-classifier** module (Bokulich *et al.*, 2018) based on **scikit-learn**. The classification extracts the likelihoods that a given “word” of 8 base pairs matches a given taxon. According to Wang *et al.* (2007), Naïve Bayes classifiers have error rates similar to that team’s earlier SeqMatch classifier (which in term has outperformed the more conventional BLAST search in that metric), but are more robust against the underlying database’s classification errors.

Diversity analysis For reference in comparison with other microbiome analyses, and to spot large discrepancies between the collection methods, alpha diversity was calculated using the Simpson index as implemented in **QIIME**’s **q2-diversity** package. The index value D is defined as area of the squares over the individual sequences’ relative abundances.

These calculations were not used in further analysis, and are depicted in figure 5 in appendix D for further reference.

2.9. Taxonomic assignments to the built tree

Taxa on different levels were chosen manually for labelling in tree visualizations; the table in figure 2 lists them. Criteria for choosing these taxa were to describe the macrostructure of the found trees, and to describe groups in the tree that are either large in number of sequences or in number of reads, both balanced against keeping trees visually readable. In addition, noteworthy taxa from related projects were added.

The selected taxa were assigned to be shown in visualizations on each highest node of the tree for which all sequences below the node (i. e., all sequences of its child leaf nodes) were assigned to the selected taxon's specification by the database lookups, or at least can possibly match the taxon (i. e., when the database result is uncertain or unidentified, but matches the selected taxon to the extent it can).

For taxa that match a large sub-tree with singular exceptions, these exceptions have been used to alter the labelling algorithm in order to keep plots readable: Specific other taxa's sequences are tolerated below a node. These other taxa are always visualized in the plots, and pointed out explicitly in the plot labelling. See page 17 for an illustrative example.

2.10. Classifying collection methods through their microbiome

To identify which groups of collection methods could be separated, a random forest prediction model was trained and evaluated. The model predicts the collection method based on the frequency table (which lists the number of reads of each cleaned up sequence in each sample). As training and evaluating on the same data set would inevitably lead to overfitting (to the point where each sample would be assigned its original collection method with near perfect accuracy), a nested cross-validation (NCV) approach was chosen. Ten different models were trained, each excluding a 10% selection of the samples. All samples were subsequently evaluated through the model that excluded them from its training set. The complete NCV process was used as implemented in **QIIME's q2-sample-classifier** package.

To find the distinguishing microorganisms, a prediction model was trained over the full set of samples. As the random forest classifier produces scalar importance values per feature (also called Gini importance), highly influential sequences could be looked up in the taxonomic mapping or the built tree.

2.11. Verifying partial flow samples

Editorial note: The analysis performed here turned out to be unsuitable for the obtained data; it was left in this text to document what has been tried, and aid in the future selection of better aerosol flow comparisons.

From the first descriptions of the GSP and impactor samples, it was assumed in early stages of this project that the air flow sampled in the impactor stages would be a subset of the sampled air flow of the GSP sampler. (This assumption was later not corroborated by the samplers' descriptions). It was further assumed that the rates of occurrence of different microorganisms would be preserved through preparation. (This assumption did also not hold, see section 3.4). If these assumptions held, a statistical test could be conducted on the microbiome data. The test would be designed around the null hypothesis of the samplers performing as described (with one aerosol flow being a subset of another, or, in different setups, two sampled flows being taken from the same aerosol). Rejection of that null hypothesis should then indicate that the samplers did not perform as expected.

As occurrences of organisms in sampled volumes can be expected to follow a Poisson distribution (McMurry, 2000), a test for comparing Poisson distributions is used to assess the null hypothesis.

In the single-value case (e.g. comparing particle counts or total DNA reads), the hypothesis can be tested using *C*-test (conditional test), which is summarized well by Krishnamoorthy and Thomson (2004). (They also provide a more powerful test for Poisson means comparison, but the added complexity would not benefit this analysis). The *C*-test internally uses a binomial test for whether the total events are distributed evenly between the two samples, and can be applied for one-sided or two-sided alternative hypotheses for subsets of flows and identical flows, respectively.

2.11.1. Adjustments for scaling factors and their variation

When the biological sample is expected to vary by a constant factor between the flows, the test needs to be modified accordingly by adjusting the event rates. This is required for this experiment's conditions due to the different air flow rates through the samplers. If later processing introduced additional scaling factors (such as pooling different volumes of PCR product after indexing), these too would need to be considered. For the evaluation in section 3.4, no such scaling was done, as it would have been lost in normalization anyway.

Any variation in the sampling conditions would be observed as superimposed on the Poisson distribution. While this is the case (e.g. with the sampling duration given in minutes having a uniform distribution error from its quantization alone, which proportionally affects the measured rate), these effects are assumed to be small compared to the variation from sampling organisms.

2.11.2. *p*-value correction for comparing multiple samples

To make better use of the available data, the test is not performed only on the total number of reads. It is additionally performed by comparing read numbers for each sequence found in either sample, or by comparing sums over read numbers across a branch of the tree (of which the total read number is the ultimate form).

Performing multiple comparisons and rejecting the null hypothesis if any test value is lower than the significance level would incorrectly reject it too easily. Figuratively speaking, it would mean checking so often that one is sure to catch the unlikely type I error.

A common default correction mechanism is Bonferroni correction; however, that is extremely conservative and unlikely to produce usable results with the given number of samples. (When applied 100 times, any test would need to exceed an individual significance level of 0.0005 at a total level of the usual 0.05).

The Benjamini-Hochberg correction, provided in the R `stats` package as an implementation based on Benjamini and Hochberg (1995), is a powerful multiple comparison procedure but requires the tests to be independent. That independence rules out performing the test simultaneously on a node and any of its parents.

With the option of aggregating multiple data points, a suitable depth needs to be chosen from the space spanned by comparing only the total number of reads and pairwise comparing the number of reads for each individual sequence.

Neither extreme is necessarily suitable: If a diverse group of organisms is present in one sample and not the other, their number could be insignificant for the total number, but at the individual sequence level (where there might be just two or three reads in a sample) the comparison against the zero reads in the other sample would be too weak.

For all distances d from the tree's root, the frequency table was aggregated to contain the sum of all reads of a branch of the rooted tree for branches starting above that distance. The aggregated frequency table for $d = 0$ thus contains a single value per sample (the total number of reads), whereas the aggregated frequency table for the maximum distance is the original frequency table with one row per sequence. Figuratively speaking, a vertical line was drawn through the trees of figure 2: All branches right of it were pooled together into the point on the line they stemmed from.

As the underlying data proved to be unsuitable for the obtained data (see section 3.4), all aggregations to be compared were arbitrarily normalized. They were scaled down such that their total read counts would be identical. Tests were thus performed for the null hypothesis of identical streams (which they, under that normalization, would be) and a two-sided alternative hypothesis. This completely invalidates any numeric results obtained from the test, but allows better reasoning about the failures of the approach. Data from quantitative PCR (qPCR) performed on the original samples might be used to justify such scaling, but would not lead to more acceptable results due to frequent comparisons to a read count of zero.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Microbiome overview

A coarse overview of the taxonomic classification of fungi across all samples (table 4a) shows that a variety of groups was found. Noteworthy entries are *Wallemia* (largely *Wallemia sebi*) and *Aureobasidium* (exclusively *Aureobasidium pullulans*), which together constitute about half the fungi reads. *Taphrina betulina* is a noteworthy rarer entry due to its original discovery in birches.

The corresponding table 4b for bacteria shows similar diversity already at the level of orders. The entry *Chloroplasts* shows that the steps in section 2.6 did not completely clear out organelles. (Yet they succeeded in removing large portions of plant DNA: the comparison sequencing of material obtained by excision of the mitochondrial bands contained up to 100% organelle or unidentified DNA in the unreliable preliminary processing steps before they were removed from the data pool).

Pivoting into the sample properties, the clearest differences were seen between collection methods. Figure 1a illustrates that in fungi, *Ascomycota* are more commonly found in catkin samples, whereas the smaller aerosol fractions (impactor stages A and

Taxon	Abundance	Taxon	Abundance
<i>Wallemia</i>	38.0%	Burkholderiaceae	27.0%
<i>Aureobasidium</i>	20.5%	Chloroplast	25.9%
<i>Irpea</i>	8.9%	Comamonadaceae	10.2%
Polyporaceae	8.7%	Burkholderiales	5.2%
<i>Trametes</i>	5.6%	Propionibacterineae	4.9%
a) Dothideomycetes	3.7%	b) Bacteria	4.5%
<i>Taphrina</i>	3.7%	Betaproteobacteria	2.3%
Fungi	1.1%	Sphingomonadaceae	2.3%
Didymellaceae	1.1%	Pseudomonadaceae	1.7%
Pleosporaceae	1.1%	Chitinophagaceae	1.7%
Others	7.6%	Others	14.1%

Table 4: Abundances of top ten taxa in fungi (left) and bacteria (right). Taxa are abbreviated to groups in fungi and order in bacteria (or as available; consequently, unidentified sequences are listed as Fungi or Bacteria).

Figure 1: Overviews of the fungi (left) and bacteria (right) microbiomes. Colors indicate top-level categories of the respective databases (phylum for fungi, domain for bacteria). Shading indicates classification by genus within the top-level category (not labeled). Taxa are consistently sorted by overall read count.

B/C/D) contained more *Basidiomycota*. The shaded parts (indicating classification by groups) show that also in finer grained classification, distribution is not uniform between sampling methods.

The analogous figure for bacteria does not show such a clear trend in the microbiomes, considering that the chloroplast fraction is more an indication of an abundance of plant material than part of the actual microbiome.

3.2. Microbiome details

For further exploration, and to give an intuitive overview of the fungal microbiome's structure, figure 2 shows both the rooted tree representing the grouping of the 339 distinct fungi sequences by similarity, and the relative frequency of these reads in all the 78 samples, grouped by sampling method.

Like figure 1, it indicates that there are clades that are predominantly present on the catkins themselves and become rarer when looking at smaller particle fractions, and vice versa. While it affirms the general trend of Basidiomycota dominating the smaller fractions, it also shows that narrower clades sometimes deviate from the larger pattern, as Tremellales does. Alternative groupings (by the birch, or blooming stage) show no such immediately visible distinction.

It also illustrates the suitability of the ITS region for taxonomic assignments: Barely any of the labels assigned as per section 2.9 show up more than once in the generated tree, and in the two cases where they do, they are always close together in the tree's metric, compared to other taxa. This indicates that individual sequences inside a taxon are likely to be clustered with individuals of the same taxon that can be identified, and conversely inspires trust in the database's consistency.

Interpreting the tree labels Looking at a few selected examples helps understand the labelling: The Ascomycota in the figure 2a are recognized as a single clade, with *Taphrina betulina* (TB) being the furthest away from the other Ascomycota. Not all reads under the labelled node would necessarily need to be identified as *Taphrina betulina* (although for this particular data set they were): if any of its nodes were only identified as *Taphrina* (or even just Fungi), the label would still stay in place as long as the classification does not contradict the label. The label was not set at its parent node because of the two sequences identified as *Taphrina carpini* (not labelled) in a sibling node.

The Basidiomycota (Ba) label is set in two places in the tree, which indicates disagreement between the rooted tree built from the ITS sequence similarities and the taxonomic classification. However, overall matching is still good: one of the two clades of Basidiomycota is just barely more similar to the Ascomycota than to the rest of Basidiomycota, which is not surprising considering the breadth the two groups span. One of the identified Basidiomycota nodes solely contains Wallemiomycetes (Wm), which is indicated by it carrying a Ba/Wm label.

In contrast, bacterial reads appear far less structured. For example, Firmicutes (Fi) are identified both as a moderately sized contiguous clade and smaller occurrences

Figure 2: Read numbers of fungi (a) and bacterial (b) sequences, normalized by sample, with dark shades indicating more reads. Samples are sorted roughly by descending size of the input material from left to right; within the sampling methods, data points are sorted by birch and (where multiple samples were taken) repetition. Vertical axis has no semantics other than grouping. The abbreviations of species hypotheses, expanded in the tables, were placed in the tree as described in section 2.9.

spread throughout the tree. This can be explained by the 16S copies inside the Firmicutes genome, which are large in number and thus prone to larger sequence variation (Větrovský and Baldrian, 2013). A noteworthy group are the Burkholderiales (B): For labelling purposes, they were configured to tolerate the presence of chloroplasts (Ch) and Alphaproteobacteria (Al), because a group of these “sits deeply inside” several well identified Burkholderiales. While the Alphaproteobacteria identification is questionable (merely one read), several chloroplast sequences were identified across different samples with high classifier confidence – making a classification error an unlikely cause. Literature search around the relation between Burkholderiales and chloroplast revealed no plausible relation.

3.3. Microorganisms specific to collected fractions

Figure 3: Accuracy of predictions from NCV evaluation of a random forest analysis for finding the sampling method from the read frequencies in fungi (left) and bacteria (right). Normalized to row sums.

Results from the NCV training are depicted in figure 3, and show that the fungi microbiome can be used to clearly predict whether a sample was drawn from catkin as opposed to any of the aerosol samples. The dark area at the left shows that aerosol samples are rarely predicted to be catkin samples; the less distinct dark area at the top shows that catkin samples are rarely predicted to be aerosol samples.

The model also gets the distinction between passive and actively collected samples right more often than not (indicated by the slightly decreased top and left intensities of the remaining rectangle), but does not distinguish well between impactor stages A and B/C/D.

The sequences with the highest importance in the random forest classification between sampling methods were classified as *Aureobasidium pullulans*, *Taphrina betulina* and *Irpex lacteus*, followed by a large number of individually less important but more numerous *Wallemia sebi* sequences. One sequence was found to be important that was not precisely identified (a member of the Ascomycota, whose neighbouring sequences in the rooted tree are no better identified). While ranked in the top 10 of influential sequences, its influence compared to the total of other taxa is low.

It should be noted here that random forest analysis is, as the name implies, a stochastic process. Importance values vary with each run; the above-mentioned taxa generally ranked high. Likewise, the precise prediction results vary; the described properties were found with all used random seeds.

With bacteria, the picture is less clear: Several taxa (chloroplasts, various Burkholderiales including *Cupriavidus* and *Propionibacterium*) were indicated as influential and those also stood out in figure 2. But their importance is ranked lower, and the overall classification is only slightly better than random.

The same NCV training on the classification categories birch (one per tree) and blooming stage (before / during / after bloom) produce did not succeed in classifying the samples. These categories might still have an impact on the microbiome; processing them separately by sample size might make that visible. The present data set contained too few samples to perform NCV at that level.

3.3.1. Alternative evaluation methods

The convenient guide² provided with **scikit-learn** (Pedregosa *et al.*, 2011) (on which **QIIME**'s classifiers are based) indicates that rather than a random forest analysis, a Linear Support Vector Classification (SVC) model should be used. Executing the NCV pipeline using that method did lead to stronger classifications, shown appendix D in figure 6. However, the importance assigned to individual reads in the SVC model is not scalar but vectorial (and thus not ordered), giving no immediate insight into their relevance for classification.

Summarizing, there are clear indications present that the microbiomes on birch catkin and pollen differ, and hints at differences between the different collection methods except for the individual impactor stages. Revisiting the situation with a more thorough sequencing run and a better understanding of Linear SVC classification might allow a more definite statement about the differences in aerosol fractions.

3.4. Evaluation of the partial flow tests

The original plans for the partial flow tests neglected to account for the fact that sequencing preparation is done with a high fidelity polymerase that makes no claim to produce quantitative results; a qPCR polymerase would have been needed (which would sacrifice the obtained sequences' accuracy). There are approaches to obtain both quantitative and sequence-preserving PCR results, such as Zhang *et al.* (2017) or Yang *et al.* (2005), but these are few, and they are not well-established for microbiome analyses.

Apart from theoretical considerations, the issue is visually apparent: Comparing the FungiQuant gel intensities of the explorative steps in section 2.4 (ranging from barely visible bands to overexposed) with the quality control performed in section 2.5 (with band intensities not even an order of magnitude apart) dispels any illusions of a constant amplification factor.

²https://scikit-learn.org/stable/tutorial/machine_learning_map/index.html

Figure 4: p values of the C -test to reject the null hypothesis of the GSP and the sum of the impactor stages come from the same Poisson distribution. The left subfigure depicts fungi results for birch 6, the right bacteria results for birch 3. Lines indicate the minimum p values, dots indicate p values from less distinct clades.

Selected³ results from comparing the GSP reads with the impactor totals are shown in figure 4. The null hypothesis that all reads in a birch’s GSP sample are taken from the same Poisson distribution as the corresponding sum reads of the impactor stages. Note that these comparisons are not sound for both the above reasons and due to the scaling described in section 2.11.2; they merely serve to illustrate what originally expected results might look like under different conditions. The plots indicate the corrected p values of the C -test comparing the read counts of aggregates, with the aggregation depth varying from 0 (only comparing the total read count) to the tree depth (comparing all sequences’ read counts pairwise).

Reading from left to right, the p values start at 1; this was to be expected given that the samples were normalized by the very value that is being compared. As the depth exceeds the point where the top level clades separate, p values plotted as a function of the depth already decrease way below the common value of $\alpha = 0.05$. This would already lead to the rejection of the hypothesis of equal input material – the large difference between, in the left (fungi) example, the Wallemiomycetes counts in the GSP and impactor samples is already unlikely to be explained by a Poisson distribution. Progressing deeper into the tree, clades are being split off, increasing the number of C -tests being performed and thus weakening the individual p -values. This affects not only the most relevant value (the minimum, depicted as a line) but also all other values (shown as dots), which represent the p values of tests done on clades that diverge less. At a depth of $d = 0.27$, the tree branches in such a way that the GSP sample contains significantly more reads along one branch than the impactor (and vice versa in the other), providing additional evidence that strengthens the rejection – to the point where even the weakening by the introduction of more tests causes no visible change any more. The bacteria sample on the right shows a similar picture; here, (relatively) weak additional evidence against the null hypothesis shows up several times before it levels out.

³Depicted are 2 of the 3 birch repetitions for which there are visible results at all even after normalization. All other sample groups show plot lines that visually go to $p = 0$ immediately.

The hope in setting up this analysis was that volume streams would not support rejection of the hypothesis at either extreme of the aggregation depth, but that evidence of differences between the streams would be found at some depth. In a plot similar to figure 4, that might show as a line that generally stays above $\alpha = 0.05$ but goes below the confidence threshold in some depth range at which the difference is detected.

3.4.1. Model re-evaluation

In parallel to the overall result, looking at individual data points shows frequent occurrences of zero counts that are compared to dozens of reads in the compared sample, often paired with opposite results on a different sequence. Even with quantitative PCR data available, no scaling of them would evade rejection in the C -test.

Between the documented Poisson distribution of particles in aerosols and the reads obtained from sequencing, a number of causes can lead to rejection:

Actual differences in the particle streams (the original alternative hypothesis) can cause rejection by design.

The different specifications of the sampling devices already violate the precondition of the flows being identical (or subsets of each other): The impactor stages are defined in terms of particle size cut-offs, the GSP sampler in terms of the DIN EN 481:1993 that deals in respiratory interaction. Further causes are discussed for the benefit of later experiments that might satisfy that condition.

Zero values are a frequent issue in sequence counts. Silverman et al. (2020) describe their causes as well as approaches for modelling them, with modelling still being subject to some controversy.

They separate causes for zeros in three categories: Sampling, biological and technical zeros. Biological zeros (i. e., the absence of the sequence from the biological system) are inapplicable as compared samples were taken from the biological sample. Technical zeros would be introduced by sample preparation effects, such as limited amplification of GC-rich sequences. Due to the identical processing of the samples, these effects should affect all of them in the same way. Sampling zeros are the effect of sequences being present in the processed sample but merely not drawn; these alone would not lead to a rejection if the assumed distribution function matches the sampling reality.

The Poisson distribution was assumed based on the known distribution of measured physical particles in aerosols. In biological environments negative binomial (also called Poisson-Gamma) models often replace Poisson models; in this case that was not an option for lack of repetitions to estimate the dispersion parameter.

While the Poisson distribution is well documented (McMurry, 2000) to work for particle distributions, the sequence reads might not be distributed like that for several reasons:

1. Accumulated errors during processing are overlaid onto the distribution in the biological sample. Examples thereof are errors in the sampling time, flow rate, and pipetting errors. These could be tested for if measurements were taken in duplicates.
2. Any single sequence in the biological sample is amplified in the PCR process. Even if all copies of a sequence are amplified by the same factor (which would rather be the case with qPCR), the assumptions of a Poisson distribution would be violated.

How badly this affects the test's validity depends on the original sample sizes and read numbers: At the limits, a degenerate sequencing run with only a single sample, taken from constantly amplified sample of many (possibly different) sequences, will produce a distribution identical to sampling the unamplified sequences. On the other extreme, sequencing every single strand of PCR product from a small sample (e. g. two copies of one sequence, and three of another) would produce a distribution with read counts in large discrete steps, with properties highly dissimilar to the original distribution.

As the effect of amplification is absent for some extreme parameters, it might be tolerable if the number of reads on a sample is much smaller than the number of sequences in the original sample. The presence of unique reads can be an indication that the number of reads is at least not much larger than the original number of sequences.

3. Single organisms can carry multiple copies of the same gene. These vary in number and sequence (see *Firmicutes* example in section 3.2). Different sequences per organism do little harm to the result's validity, but might require using a less powerful p -value correction method due to compared values being correlated. When organisms carry identical copies of a sequence, adjustments for the copy number variability might be made. The data available in RDP database (Wang *et al.*, 2007) would not suffice for this purpose as it only provides a mean copy number for any taxon, not the copy number's variability.
4. Multiple organisms can reside on a single particle, and arrival in groups is a textbook example (Wikipedia, 2022) of violation of Poisson assumptions. While this could be an interesting observation if determined to be the only remaining explanation of a hypothesis rejection, this effect would best be detected with low numbers of sequences in the biological samples and high numbers of reads, putting it in conflicts with the above requirements for reducing the effects of amplification.

In summary, while individual issues with this approach might be addressed, there are several major impediments that would need to be overcome to perform the envisioned comparison – the largest being that the experiments' sampling methods could not be expected to sample sub-flows of each other, and the lack of polymerases that are both sequence preserving and quantitative. Additionally, the bacteria excision process is too imprecise to warrant quantitative comparison, and even the variation in the extraction

process might need additional samples to allow more accurate (e. g. negative binomial) modelling. All these indicate that the simple partial flow checks, which were originally envisioned to be executed automatically and without additional manual effort as part of future aerosol microbiome projects, can not be achieved in this way.

3.5. Workflow enhancements for organelle exclusion

Given that the excision process used between the bacterial PCR stages was clearly not suitable for any quantitative comparison (as evidenced by the large variation in volume after the gel filtration step), and on top of that, error prone, alternative approaches for removing organelle DNA were considered: a third type of oligonucleotide sequences could be added to PCR mix. They would be similar to primers, but matching organelle sequences at some point between the primers, and preventing the chain reaction (e. g. using 3'-terminus alterations).

The use of peptide nucleic acid (PNA) PCR clamps to silence plant organelle DNA has been described by Kawasaki and Ryan (2020); their approach enhanced the sensitivity to bacteria, but did not remove the need for gel excision in real soil samples. A similar but more complex approach by (Song and Xie, 2020) performed better on synthetic samples by using the CRISP-Cas9 system to cut plastid and mitochondrial DNA before amplification.

These approaches were not known at the time of the experimental design, but should be considered for follow-up projects, especially when combined with quantitative methods. Sequencing results of this project could be used in selecting suitable clamps. Reads that should be considered for this are both chloroplasts as identified in the regular samples, and (after a more powerful sequencing run, or when processing them as single-ended reads) from the sequencing data of the 900 bp mitochondrial samples.

3.6. Workflow enhancements for used software tools

At several stages of the processing setup, the author produced erroneous results by entering data into pipelines in which they would not fit, or by manually implementing conversions between data formats. In all cases, the error could have been prevented if standardized data formats with defined extension points were used. In their absence, conversion routines that preserve metadata can avoid some misuse. For two concrete cases, such a conversion has been suggested⁴ or implemented⁵.

4. Conclusion and outlook

4.1. Comparing partial flows

The attempt to provide an easy-to-use automated check for comparing multiple aerosol flows met with several critical obstacles. While some of these might be overcome by

⁴<https://forum.qiime2.org/t/import-from-bam-files-tool-or-tutorial/21988>

⁵<https://github.com/qiime2/q2-types/issues/269>

larger input data sets, the lack of quantitative amplification in sequence-accurate PCR stands out as a roadblock. Unless process in suitable polymerases is made, this topic will not be revisited.

4.2. Further processing of amplified samples

The sequencing format used to produce the present data (MiSeq PE250 Nano) was chosen as a cost efficient initial explorative step. As the collection and extraction did succeed in finding microorganisms whose presence varies with the collection method, a sequencing run with more reads and longer reads is being prepared.

That data might help answer a few open questions – e.g. whether the low quality scores at the denoising stage might be due to the sequencing method, and whether full sequencing of the 900 bp mitochondrial fragments can help in selecting clamps that would simplify the processing of bacterial samples. When evaluating that data, a Linear SVC prediction could be used to improve over the Random Forest results, provided a suitable norm on its importance values is found.

Data from that sequencing run could also help designing bespoke PNA clamps or guide RNA for CRISP-Cas9 based organelle exclusion. Their use was originally considered to ensure quantitative processing of samples (which the used polymerases do not provide anyway). Establishing these exclusion mechanisms can still be a valuable contribution to the workflow by reducing manual and error prone processing steps.

4.3. Sampling microorganisms from birches

The selected sample processing and sequencing workflow was successful in finding varied microbiomes both in birch catkins and their aerosols. Their main inhabitants are *Wallemia*, *Aureobasidium* and Burkholderiales.

When the effect of microbiome on pollen on the allergenic potential is studied further, it makes sense to apply aerosol sampling methods to birch pollen: sampling of full plant parts produces different microbiomes than the pollen itself, and even the collection method (passive sampling vs. GSP sampling vs. cascade impactor) might make a difference, Conversely, when studying changes of allergenicity induced by microorganisms on the plant, sampling of pollen may not produce relevant results.

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B. Reproducibility

The author values reproducible research, especially in the digital realm where it is attainable. All data, as well as revision controlled source code for text, graphics and analyses is provided in the accompanying archive and can be used to recreate the figures and calculations.

Software versions used to build this report are those part of Debian GNU/Linux version sid as of 2022-04-18; **QIIME** packages not distributed through there were used through the Docker container distributed as part of its 2022.2 release.

C. Acronyms and abbreviations

16S a DNA region storing the ribosomal RNA sequence of the ribosomes' 16S subunit (a typical barcoding region of bacteria)

AIT AIT Austrian Institute of Technology 3

BAM Binary Sequence Alignment Map 10

DADA Divisive Amplicon Denoising Algorithm

FASTQ *FASTA* (a sequence file format) with additional quality information

GSP Gesamtstaubprobenahme 6

ITS internal transcribed spacer (typical barcoding region of fungi)

JSS Journal of Statistical Software 3

LPS lipopolysaccharide 4

MAFFT Multiple Alignment using Fast Fourier Transform 11

NCV nested cross-validation 13

NGS Next Generation Sequencing 5

PCR polymerase chain reaction	5
PNA peptide nucleic acid	24
qPCR quantitative PCR	15
SVC Support Vector Classification	20
VBCF Vienna BioCenter Core Facilities	10

D. Auxiliary materials

This section contains tables and plots which are included for sake of completeness.

Designation Fabrication	Usage
0.01% Tween buffer Diluted 1:10 000 from Tween 20.	Initial storage of samples
Agarose gel 2% _{m/v} (or 1% _{m/v}) By mixing 2 g (or 1 g) agarose in 100 mL of TAE buffer, heating in a 750 W microwave and shaking manually until homogenous.	DNA separation (DNA excision)
TAE buffer By diluting 50× TAE buffer with deionized water.	Agarose gel fabrication
Water (PCR grade) Shipped with GoTaq master mix.	PCR assays, see table 2
GoTaq mix 2× From vendor Promega, GoTaq Green Master Mix, 2× M7123.	Polymerase/buffer/dNTP in PCR assays, see table 2
Q5 From vendor Promega, Q5 High Fidelity DNA Polymerase M0491S, 2000 U/mL. Package includes suitable buffer and solved dNTP in separate tubes.	Polymerase in PCR assays, see table 2

Table 5: Stock solution used. Unless otherwise noted, these were shared across the laboratory.

Type	Designation	Vendor	Product	Usage
GSP sampler	—	GSP3,5	GSA	sample collection
Impactor	—	SKC	Sioutas Cascade Impactor	sample collection
PCR	HBR-ID 260	Bio-Rad	C1000 Touch Thermal Cycler / CFX384 Real-Time System	nested PCR
PCR	HBR-ID 201	peqlab	peqSTAR 96X	Index PCR
Ribolyzer	HBR-ID 39	MP	FastPrep-24	DNA extraction
Gel station	—	Bio-Rad	ChemiDoc XRS+	Visual evaluation of gels
centrifuge	HBR-ID 982	Eppendorf	Centrifuge 5425	All centrifugation of tubes up to 2 mL
centrifuge	—	eppendorf	Centrifuge 5810 R	All centrifugation of plates and larger containers
vacuum con- centrator	—	SP Scientific	miVac SpeedTrap	Reducing samples (≤ 2 mL)
freeze dryer	HBR-ID 83	Christ	Alpha 2-4 LSC	Reducing samples (> 2 mL)
lab robot	HBR-ID 888	Hamilton	Microlab Star M	DNA extraction
spectrophoto- meter	HBR-ID 404	DeNovix	DS-11 FX+	DNA concentration measurements before sequencing

Table 6: Machines utilized during this project

Figure 5: Simpson diversity index of fungi (left) and bacterial (right) sequences, depending on collection method. The value of 0 indicates a sample that contained only identical sequences, and thus has no diversity.

Figure 6: Accuracy of predictions from NCV evaluation of a Linear SVC analysis for finding the sampling method from the read frequencies in fungi (left) and bacteria (right). Normalized to row sums.

E. Protocol of DNA extraction

This appendix details the DNA extraction steps for section 2.3. It largely reproduces the handbook of the Qiagen MagAttract Power Soil DNA EP Kit (QIAGEN, 2018); deviations are explicitly annotated and explained. The second half of the protocol can be performed manually (for small numbers of samples) or in an automated fashion. The kit's handbook describes the latter; the former is based on AIT's established variation thereof. All Solutions mentioned in this section are all part of the MagAttract Power Soil DNA EP Kit from Qiagen.

All samples had been dried, and were resuspended in 750 μL PowerBead Solution and 4 μL RNase A Solution.

Mechanical extraction The suspensions were placed in 2 mL screw-top tubes together with 60 μL Solution SL as well as roughly 1.29 g of beads (Lysing Matrix Y, MP Biomedical). The tubes were shaken in a ribolyzer at a setting of 6 $\frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$ for 3×20 s.

The samples were centrifuged (15 060 rpm, 5 min⁶) and the supernatant transferred to a stock 96-well plate. (The use of tubes up to the plate transfer is diverging from the vendor instructions that call for bead beating in plates; these workflows established at AIT match the available devices).

Inhibitor Removal 450 μL of Solution IR were added to each tube, vortexed for 5 s and left to incubate at 4 °C for at least 10 min.

Pellet removal The tubes were centrifuged twice (again, 15 060 rpm, 5 min), with the supernatant transferred to new tubes between the runs, avoiding the pellet. After the second centrifugation, the supernatant was transferred to a vessel as indicated by the following process, again avoiding any pellet.

E.1. Manual DNA extraction

Manual DNA extractions starts in 2 mL tubes.

Binding To each tube, 850 μL Binding Solution was added, as well as 20 μL of freshly vortexed Zorb Reagent (also called ClearMag Beads). The tubes were vortexed on a shaker heated to 55 °C for 10 min at 1000 rpm.

Washing For a total of 4 times, the beads were left to settle on a magnetic plate for 15 minutes, and the supernatant discarded. Between the settling steps, 500 μL of Wash Solution was added to each tube, and vortexed briefly.

⁶Centrifugation parameters are given in rpm for consistency with the facility's established device default settings. At the used Eppendorf 5425, this setting corresponds to $21\,300 \times g_n$

Elution To each tube's pellet pellet, 100 μ L Elution Buffer were added, and the tubes were vortexed for 15 min at 1000 rpm. After a final sedimentation phase of 10 min on the magnetic plate, the supernatant was transferred to new tubes for storage.

E.2. Automated DNA extraction

The automated version starts in a 96-well plate matching the robot's specification.

Steps followed the epMotion protocol provided with the kit executed on a lab robot. It was stocked with the same solutions as in the manual extraction, and a magnetic plate.

The automated steps of the extraction were managed by Michael Stierschneider or his team at AIT, and not part of the graded work.